

Review Article

Increase Incidences Tuberculosis in Diabetic Patients in Developing Countries

Akanksha Mishra, MA

International Studies, College of Arts and Sciences, University of San Francisco, 2130 Fulton Street, San Francisco, CA 94117-1080

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Abstract

Relationship between Diabetes mellitus and tuberculosis is going on from decades though available literature leaves no doubt that they are interrelated, the rate of it is still high in countries where the environment for living is poor. This relationship further confirms to be an example of an association between a communicable and non-communicable disease. Due to the absence of proper amenities for hygiene and population overcrowding in countries a major problem. Malnutrition is one of the major causes of increase detection of tuberculosis followed by diabetes mellitus amongst the population. Additionally, obesity in the populations with diabetes is also the risk factor for increase tuberculosis in the developing countries. Thus, an increase incidence of tuberculosis in observed globally in diabetic population, in particular to the developing countries needs attention of health care provider before it become epidemic.

Early 20th century researchers started coming forward with reports on treating the tuberculosis, as it was more now a serious health subject in developing countries. Diabetes was observed to be more in patients suffering with tuberculosis with a percentile to be 5.6%, 7.3% and 14.8% in populations from India, Turkey and Indonesia (1, 2, 3). Additionally, a relationship of type 2 diabetes mellitus (DM) on the clinical severity and treatment outcome in patients with tuberculosis (TB) is reported (2, 3).

Reports indicates that China depicts every year about 1.5 million new TB cases with approximately 270,000 TB deaths (WDF) (5). China accounts therefore a global burden of nearly 17% with at least 100 million affected with DM. Similarly India according to data of 2011 accounts for about 61.3 million suffering from DM while 1.98 million people get TB with about 300,000 people who die every year (5). Likewise in Indonesia approximately 450,000 new TB cases get registered every year with deaths with TB numbering about 64,000

making Indonesia as number 6 in rank globally in terms of DM exposed patients. Even though awareness about the possible consequences of the dual disease now exists in almost all Asian countries with a high TB-DM burden, there are still many questions to be addressed (8). This review gives a global overview of epidemiological researches related to TB-DM comorbidity, placing special attention on the TB-DM epidemic in developing Asian countries (WDF) and trying methods which would improve diabetes screening among tuberculosis patients (WDF12-621. Gentoft: World Diabetes Foundation) (8). Several reports indicate that tuberculosis is becoming a big chronic health problem in the developing countries particularly in the low income individuals. Obesity, diet and physical activity are leading causes for the increase incidences of severe tuberculosis related to diabetic mellitus (7, 11, 13, 19-21). Interestingly, the relationship between TB and DM has been noticed for years but studying cases along with clinical judgments has taken scientists towards public health due to rarely reported TB in high income countries compare to increase incidences of DM; whereas, DM is likely noticed to be insignificant progression of TB is affected by *Mycobacterium tuberculosis (Mtb)* bacteria followed by tuberculosis bacilli infection leading towards an active process of the disease which is marked by a two-step process, controlled by exogenous and endoge-

nous risk influences. Meanwhile the endogenous factors influence it by leading the infection from the progression towards active disease of tuberculosis and DM is related to micro vascular damage, which may comprise of retinopathy, nephropathy and neuropathy (9).

Countries Burdened with Diabetes mellitus (DM) and Tuberculosis (TB)

Developing countries are seeing the global rise in DM because TB being widespread has resulted in making the populations at risk for diseases. It is assumed that in the coming 20 years it shall be seen that at least 75% of population will have DM in countries whose population is exposed to TB. Recent data shows that countries like Saudi Arabia, Russia and Indonesia have at least 10%–30% of people suffering from the coexistence of TB and DM (19). Prediction by various studies reported a rise in the diabetic population from 285 million towards 439 million, leading to a rise of ~ 3.5 million deaths in the coming years till 2030. Low income and developing countries like Asia, India, Iran and China have most of the 80% patients living with DM and around 70% of diabetics live in TB prevalent countries as reported by the World Health Organization (WHO) (19). Prediction by various studies reported a rise in the diabetic population from 285 million towards 439 million, leading to a rise of ~ 3.5 million deaths in the coming

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Pulmonary TB is the ninth most frequent complication of DM and due to a rising prevalence of DM, the relative contribution of DM to the TB epidemic is increasing". Since Type 2 diabetes mellitus (DM) is major widespread in countries with low and middle incomes (LMICs), it increases the risk of control and as DM is also a main contributor in the active TB and becomes difficult in managing and treatment. Thus DM faces more financially a problem to countries because of limited availability of medicines. This being due to the fact for example like Africa where expenditure per capita on health is US \$30–800, whereas the cost for a diabetic care ranges from \$2144 and \$11430 (direct costs \$876–1220).(25) Low incidence of TB then DM was 14.8% in Indian population compare to the 25% in Mexico, indicates ethnicity may play an important part in the disease pathogenesis (26, 27). But another study reports that irrespective of place or ethnicity DM is definitely a risk among TB patients. This study shows that in Tanzania and Indonesia TB is associated with old age, obesity, inactive lifestyle, and family history of DM (20, 21). Furthermore, in Africa, TB and (HIV) / (A

AIDS) are becoming linked with chronic non-communicable diseases as Diabetes is getting linked to TB and TB is getting related to DM (12). Studies show that there is an increased risk of TB with Type 1 and Type 2 of DM. A study by Murray and Jeon showed that having DM gave rise to risk of developing TB (16, 17). Several studies implicate treatment failures in these countries due to lack proper screening, 4.8% of TB-DM patients with respect to 1.5% in non-diabetic TB patients. Some Low-income countries cannot afford as insulin is expensive as sometimes a wage monthly of a person is equal to the cost of insulin. Therefore socioeconomic conditions lead to chaos (22, 23). Though, it is important that all TB patients should be also screened for DM but facilities in these LMICs cannot or do not have proper equipment for screening which advances in complications and increases the risk factors in population. Thus proper techniques and collaboration between countries are important to bear this dual burden of disease. Several methods for screening, approach and technologies are put forward in detecting diabetes; however, many obstacles are faced when applied to TB patients.(28) Though TB has been seen to increase the blood glucose levels (29), which results in the false detection of a patient having DM .This has contributed in LMICs especially to have false results because the detection tools are not accurate, resulting a cost burden to TB patients as

Figure 1. Countries with low income Projected prevalent diabetes cases and current worldwide tuberculosis incidence (Map shown is taken from the publication of International Diabetes Foundation Diabetes, authored by Wild S and King H).

Preventing Methods in countries having DM screening with tuberculosis patients

WHO report diagnosed DM by any one of the following methods for example, "a fasting plasma glucose level ≥ 7.0 mmol/l (126 mg/dl); plasma glucose ≥ 11.1 mmol/l (200 mg/dl) 2 h after a 75 g oral glucose load in a glucose tolerance test; symptoms of hyperglycemia and casual plasma glucose ≥ 11.1 mmol/l (200 mg/dl); glycated hemoglobin (HbA1c) $\geq 6.5\%$ (10, 15). One can clinical diagnose also DM the next day if the patient turns out to symptomatic with the plasma

glucose levels being highly elevated. WHO has made guidelines for the countries that patients suffering from TB should use a country's rules when DM has to be detected (WHO) (7). Though some types of risk based questionnaires are sometimes used for DM in TB patients, still some noninvasive tests like blood and urine are used to check the biochemical markers or any response observed physiologically (WHO) (7, 10).

Some times drug reactions have been seen to effects DM as it leads to impaired renal function with respect to increasing the risk to the drug intake in

toxicological way causing liver injuries to patients. Some times cellular immunity has been seen that patents suffering with DM show low plasma levels in relation to anti-TB drugs (1). Though the use of Multi Drug Resistant (MDR) tuberculosis is continuing to challenge globally on the use and effect on TB patients. Researchers have studied that katG that is involved in the defending mechanism of the mycobacterium also oxidizes to the active form when seeing the influence of DM DM screening and diagnosis guidelines from a selection of the 22 countries with the highest TB burdens in the world from which information regarding national DM guidelines available is shown in Table 1. Though the presence of a preferable screening of DM is not determined but studies show that 2-hour postprandial glucose (2hPG) method is the best as it is cheap rapid and quick. It is seen that in Asian populations this method seems to be more sensitive when compared to fasting blood glucose (FBG), random blood glucose (RBG). Though the recommendations by WHO are for the HbA1c as a diagnostic test for DM.

Biochemical tests. Various biochemical diabetes-screening tests are blood or plasma glucose tests, which might include random plasma glucose (RPG), random blood glucose, fasting plasma glucose (FPG), fasting blood glucose (FBG) and the oral glucose tolerance (OGTT). (14) Glucose testing is

usually done via venous blood, which is drawn laboratory where there are instruments that can test or by glucometer testing using portable POC devices. Usually FPG and RPG and one-point measurements taken in blood usually after fasting on a patient or done randomly, whereas the OGTT measures the glucose challenge as blood glucose levels are measured before and after food intake as per the recommendation of International Diabetes Federation. Though OGTT is a gold standard for the DM diagnostic test it is costly and time consuming. Thus, FPG is preferred as it is easy and less time consuming. Other tests suggested by WHO especially for countries like South Africa and Uganda (Table 1) a urine glucose and A1c measurements, as it being less sensitive that is in addition to be used as a glycemic control monitoring test (7, 10).

Several test available for DM screening and diagnosis as mentioned in Table 2; even though, in developing countries cost for screening or trained personnel or lack of availability of test kits are a major problem. Sometimes these test are not useful for TB patients as FPG and OGTT need the patient to be prepared before hand which results the TB patient to already get in touch with health system as risks are developed as delays in sputum culture by TB patients are developed. Therefore RPG tests are done as they do not require fasting for TB patient and are more commonly use.

Test	Measures	Specimen	Test	Performance	Normal range	Pre-diabetes	Distinguishes transient hyperglycaemia
FPG, FBG	Glucose post 8 h fast	Capillary venous blood	Glucometer laboratory measurement	40-65% sensitivity, >90% specificity ¹⁷	FPG ≤99 mg/dl (7.0 mmol/l)	FPG-100-125 mg/dl (5.6-6.9 mmol/l); IFG	No
OGTT	Glucose after fasting +2h post-glucose load	Capillary venous blood	Glucometer laboratory measurement	96.8% max sensitivity, 90.8% max specificity ³⁸	2 h PGL ≤139 mg/dl (7.0 mmol/l)	140-199 mg/dl (7.8-11.0 mmol/l); IFG	No
RPG, RBG	Glucose regardless of when person last ate	Capillary venous blood	Glucometer laboratory measurement	40-79% sensitivity, 66-96% specificity ¹⁷	RPT<200 mg/dl (11/1 mmol/l)	Cannot be used to diagnose pre-diabetes	No
Urine	Presence of glucose in urine	Voided mid-stream urine	Dipstick	21-64% sensitivity; specificity >98% ¹⁷	0-15 mg/dl	>15 mg/dl	No
A1c	% of Hb that is glycated	Capillary venous blood	Glucometer laboratory measurement	78-81% sensitivity, 79-84% specificity ³⁵	A1c<5.7%	A1c= 5.7-6.4%	Yes

Table 1: DM screening and diagnosis guidelines from selected high TB burden countries (WHO)

(6, 10). Thus, test A1c is used over FPG and RPG as it does not require acid secretion thus inducing metabolism. Notably, several studies have shown to have an increase in the risk of Multi drug resistance tuberculosis (MDR TB) especially in diabetics ranging from 2.1 to 8.8 times.⁽²⁴⁾ Reports indicate that TB-DM patients have a high risk of relapsing, approximately, 4-fold risk of relapse in TB-DM versus TB-no DM (RR 3.89; 95% CI 2.43-6.23)[”] happened especially for patients in Mexico with 1262 patients who went through relapses and reinfection. Thus clinical findings of these adverse effects amongst TB-DM patients show that

more cohort studies should be done and find out ways why DM treatments fail sometimes in TB affected patients. Though, technology is developing for evaluating patients quickly but they have not been optimized for LMIC populations. Though some technologies are being used for diagnosis still they need to be used for a wide range of TB patient populations as they have not been routinely used. A brief novel DM screening technologies with a summary is provided in Table 3.

Though, bi-directional screening is needed in for TB-DM, but the

Table 2. Common DM screening and diagnostic tests^{17,35,38}

Test	Measures	Specimen	Test	Performance	Normal range	Pre-diabetes	Distinguishes transient hyperglycaemia
FPG, FBG	Glucose post 8 h fast	Capillary venous blood	Glucometer laboratory measurement	40-65% sensitivity, >90% specificity ¹⁷	FPG ≤99 mg/dl (7.0 mmol/l)	FPG-100-125 mg/dl (5.6-6.9 mmol/l); IFG	No
OGTT	Glucose after fasting +2h post-glucose load	Capillary venous blood	Glucometer laboratory measurement	96.8% max sensitivity, 90.8% max specificity ³⁸	2 h PGL ≤139 mg/dl (7.0 mmol/l)	140-199 mg/dl (7.8-11.0 mmol/l); IFG	No
RPG, RBG	Glucose regardless of when person last ate	Capillary venous blood	Glucometer laboratory measurement	40-79% sensitivity, 66-96% specificity ¹⁷	RPT<200 mg/dl (11/1 mmol/l)	Cannot be used to diagnose pre-diabetes	No
Urine	Presence of glucose in urine	Voided mid-stream urine	Dipstick	21-64% sensitivity; specificity >98% ¹⁷	0-15 mg/dl	>15 mg/dl	No
A1c	% of Hb that is glycated	Capillary venous blood	Glucometer laboratory measurement	78-81% sensitivity, 79-84% specificity ³⁵	A1c<5.7%	A1c= 5.7-6.4%	Yes

DM=diabetes mellitus; TB= tuberculosis; POC=point of care; A1c=blood glycated hemoglobin; AGE= advanced glycation end product; GA= glycated albumin; F= fructosamine.

screening methods results in difficult diagnosis after treatment on post DM or TB treatment in the developing countries. This is due to the fact that countries like India and China have a high TB population and studies show that they are already under treatment without screening.(11) Therefore, it needs to check on the cost if screening cost if screening of these patients should be only on high risk. One of the other problems is the advance technology for diagnosing TB and DM in developing countries. Low sensitivity was seen in tests of fasting glucose and oral glucose tolerance test was better on a screening base when done with HbA_{1c}.(18) The sputum smear

is less sensitive;(4) therefore, various advance technologies is needed to detect TB and DM in developing countries like rapid nucleic acid amplification technology for TB or auto fluorescence-based readers or sudomotor function devices for DM. Several, new technologies are in the process for exploring and detecting TB diagnosis with the release of Gamma Interferon, which would respond to mycobacterium and would use a bio-optical sensor technology, which has been developed by Rapid Biosensor Systems (RBS), UK. This RBS technology is a non-invasive screening solution, which is portable and gives immediate results and does not need trained

Table 3. Novel DM screening methods with potential utility in TB populations

	Distinguishes transient hyperglycemia	Low cost	No fasting	<5 min results	High sensitivity	Simple use	Non-invasive	No calibration	No minimum operating temperature	POC	Other
hydroglucitol	1-3 months	No	Yes	No	Yes	No	No	No	Yes	No	Early in development pipeline
glycated albumin fructosamine	GA-1 month F= mixed	Yes	Yes	Yes	64.1% ⁴⁷	No	No	No	No	Yes	Early in development pipeline
retinotor function	Yes	Low per test cost, high device cost	Yes	Yes	75% ⁴⁸	Yes	Yes	Yes	No	Yes	Early in development pipeline
A1c readers	3 months	Low device cost, high per test cost	Yes	Yes	78-81% ⁴⁹	Yes	No	No	No	Yes	
retinoreaders	12 months	Low per test cost, high device cost	Yes	Yes	74.7%	Yes	Yes	Yes	No	Yes	Early in development pipeline

DM=diabetes mellitus; TB= tuberculosis; POC=point of care; A1c=blood glycated hemoglobin; AGE= advanced glycation end product; GA= glycated albumin; F= fructosamine.

personnel and can be handled easily to use especially in developing countries. WHO requires all TB patients to be screened for DM but the presence of technologies is not appropriate in each country. Thus a common strategic plan is needed to fight both diseases TB and DM considering the Bali Declaration, which was signed on 3 November 2015 in Bali, Indonesia. The declaration wants one to consider double screening and an affordable cost treatment making public aware about both diseases and more research to be done in low income countries with new techniques. Combining epidemiological with clinical

and immunological studies on TB and DM. it is necessary that glucose be controlled on TB patients using test HbA1c. TB and DM patients mainly in low- and middle-income countries; therefore, guidance to these patients are necessary so that the DM technologies that are present can be put forward among the TB populations. It is necessary to understand that though screening and technology can improve the life all TB patients in all hospitals of developing countries and provide proper monitoring and care for DM so that the patients TB treatment follows smoothly.(6)

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